

Evaluation of Corporate Social Environment Responsibility of Pharmaceutical Multinational Firms in Jamshoro

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Abstract:

Wastes are the unwanted materials which can no longer be used in the manufacturing processes that can eventually turn into hazardous or non-hazardous material, to humans/environment. Management of the hazardous wastes is an integral part of pharmaceutical industries. This study aims to evaluate the current practices of CSER (Corporate Social Environment Responsibility) towards environmental pollution, waste management and the relation between CSER initiatives and company reputation and performance. Pharmaceutical waste management is an important part in pharmaceutical industries.

A cross-sectional survey was conducted in two pharmaceutical companies that are ARCHROMA and GlaxoSmithKline (GSK) working in district Jamshoro Sindh by means of suitable sampling procedure. These tools were used to determine the performance of the company by using the different questionnaire, which are divided into four sections, that is related to the basic information of CSER adopted by the Company, Waste Management and Company initiatives and reputation also check-list of company Waste Management activities.

The sample was taken with upper management, middle management, lower management. The questionnaires were distributed among these employees by using mixed method that is online and physical. Out of 50 distributed questionnaires, 39 were completed and returned, giving overall returning rate of 78%. The further study identified that how the environment like, water pollution, methane emission, soil degradation and living bodies are affected by the company. To reduce these factors which affect the environment there were also working on waste management and disposal. We found there were mostly waste was plastic bags, chemical, expiry medicines and other instruments. The method for disposal was burning the chemical, recycling and other were sent by container to hired company.

The study also measures the performance and corporate reputation of pharmaceutical companies. They were focused to initiate the CSER to maintain their company reputation and sustain their business in market. They were working for different trainings for the capacity building of the employees regarding CSER which has direct and indirect impact on the environment. The study contributes for academic research as well as for the practical implication and also for future research studies.

Key Words: CSER, GSK, ARCHROMA, Soil degradation, hazardous or non-hazardous, Waste Management.

CHAPTER 01 INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND

Corporate social responsibility is the concept where corporation take measures to ensure being socially responsible. However, this concept emerges now as multi-dimensional aspect, and environmental aspect become its major factor. Corporations around the world and especially in under developed countries are not much emphasizing on environmental perspectives which is creating environmental issues, includes airborne and skin diseases and many other health issues for the people living in surrounding of such industries. Mostly pharmaceutical industries are established in residential area where the effect of the hazardous material is more effecting on human health. Concept of corporate social responsibility is already been implemented in the European countries. Mostly countries are making environmental issues at the core of their fundamental public policies. European Union provides guidelines for the companies to make business

sustainable and the framework for the sustainable business to create better and secure working conditions for the laborers, responsible business and improved products (Naslidky.N, 2012) Environmentally social responsible business is an ideal business which are creating situations and deal with environmental agencies in coordination to make market place more sustainable to decreases the chances of causes which are effecting environment pollution and degradation (Egri.C, 2008) In the world where number of organizations are emphasizing about corporate social and environmental responsible business, it is become a norm now to being an environmental friendly business and the corporations are showing it as their brand advertisement (Deegan.M, 2016)Therefore it businesses should create a framework for the policies and guidelines to start the socially responsible business according to human rights and consumer protection rights. Business are now making their business as environmentally friendly and creating partnership with stakeholders to understand the environmental concerns. Business now a days see it as maximizing the value creating opportunity for the businesses around the world (Noked, 2013).

The environment is badly effected by their waste materials to decrease the damages from the business perspective CSER may include the following

- Energy use
- Water use
- Waste management
- Recycling
- Emissions
- Eco-friendly office and business travel policies

Normally people are concerned about quality of water, and also, they are interested to buy the products which give them and their family a benefit in their health. The companies manufactured products are popular with quality and image of the corporation (Cubie I.I .Lau 2019).

1.2 GSK Pakistan:

The origin of the Glaxo Smith Kline Pakistan Limited is derived from the combination of Smith Kline and French of Pakistan Limited, Beecham Pakistan (Private) Limited, and Glaxo introduces and started this organization in January 1, 2001, and is now it becomes Pakistan's prominent drug firm.

GSK has extended history of capitalizing in Pakistan. Glaxo Laboratories Pakistan Ltd., our ancestor company, was the first pharmaceutical company to be listed on the Karachi Stock Exchange in 1951.

Pharmaceuticals (prescription medications and vaccines) and consumer healthcare are GSK Pakistan's key business segments (over-the-counter-medicines, oral care and dietetic care). Anti-infective, Respirational, Injections, Dermatological, Gastric, Analgesics, Oncology, Urology, Central Nervous System, Allergy, Cardiovascular, and Vitamins therapy are all offered by the company in Pakistan.

We are dedicated and committed to our goals of delivering patients with first-rate

products that will help them live healthier lives. Augmentin, Seretide, Amoxil, Velosef, Zantac, and Calpol are some of our most well-known prescription products, while Panadol, Horlicks, Sensodyne, and ENO are well-known consumer healthcare brands. Protuberant vaccines include Synflorix, Infanrix Hexa, Rotarix, Engerix-B, Havrix and Priorix Tetra.

The succession of the GSK is highly appreciated with equal volume and share in the market. MNCs like Abbott, Novartis, Pfizer, and Sanofi, as well as local companies like Getz and Sami, are major competitors. GSK made its name in market with its track record and well known among his partners and integrating with successful of BMS, UCB, and Stiefel companies, as well as developing a diverse and profitable portfolio of over 150 brands.

GSK Pakistan is currently working with employs approximately 2,300 people through Sales, Global Manufacturing Services (GMS), the Pharma division, and Consumer Health Care and it will increase by

yearly after getting the success on the globe. West Wharf, F-268 location, and Korangi are the three facilities that make up our Global Manufacturing Services (GMS) in Pakistan.

1.3 ARCHROMA:

Archroma Pakistan Limited is a well-known and leading Brand & Performance Textile Specialties, and it works in the textile, paper, coatings, adhesives, sealants, and construction industries, producing, selling, and developing new products.

Archroma is a global color and specialty chemicals company that was shaped from Clariant's fiber, paper, and emulsions businesses. It is dedicated to ingenuity, first-class excellence principles, high service levels, efficiency of cost, and maintainability.

It has two production sites at Jamshoro, and Landhi, Karachi, Sindh. Archroma Center of Excellence (ACE) at Korangi Karachi and area offices in Lahore and Faisalabad.

1.4 PROBLEM STATEMENT:

Industries like pharmaceutical and chemical are working round the clock and the production department use hazardous raw materials. In fact Pharmaceutical companies are the one of most pollution emitting organizations. In result the toxic output spread around the vicinity. This research will study the environmental aspect under the umbrella of CSER. Corporate social environmental responsibility is a systematic regulation which provides guidelines to industries to implement social and environmental policies. Therefore, it is important to ascertain the sources of environmental pollution by pharmaceutical companies, determine the contribution of CSER initiatives in sustainable business practices, and evaluate the waste management system. It is also important to identify whether implementation of various environment management system has a positive influence on the firms' performance in terms of profit and reputation.

1.5 Aim and Objectives

1.5.1 Aim

Aim of this is study to explore various source of environmental pollution caused by pharmaceutical, and CSER activities done to mitigate the harmful effect of the pollutants and to compare the benefits to companies of Jamshoro district in terms of reputation and performance.

1.5.2 Objectives

1. To explore the sources of environmental pollution in pharma sector of Jamshoro.
2. To evaluate the methods of waste management adopted by the pharma companies.
3. To study the relation between CSER initiative and company's reputation and performance by evaluating two companies of Jamshoro district.

1.6 Significance of the study:

This research is focused on the practices of corporate social responsibility on its environmental aspects. By the detailed overview of research and fundamental aspects of CSER, it will provide a valuable addition to existing body of literature. For the industrial sector it will provide information to the industries to emphasis the importance of practices of CSR. This research will help industries to create the future implementation for their CSER guidelines.

Chapter 2 Literature Review

Introduction and Background:

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a concept about the companies are fulfill the needs of the stakeholders like customers, workers, employees and local communities and make the different strategies to make their business more successful and get maximum profit from the market. The most important and accurately can say that this is only working for the sake of society as a whole. The main focus of the organization is to cover the basic needs of the community and work for them which includes the environmental problems, education other training programs. It also works for the human rights that covers the employee welfare, business ethics and safety measure for them of the work force at the work station.

(Baxi & Ajit., 2005) state CSR as an responsibility of industry is to increase the values of the livelihood and sustain the economic growth and initialize the good values which helps the organization to maintain the image in the market and have the strong relationships with the stakeholders and make themselves successful in the development of the corporation. As narrated by (Rangan & chase, 2012), CSR is become as a captioned with the different names which is harmful for the company. These names are included donation, social duty and company nationality.

The main focus has been observed in the last literature that there should been relationship between the current cooperate social responsibility and the innovations. They highlighted specifically on the role by the maintainable development in business and other source of the innovation. (Klewitz and Hansen, 2014).

The captivated had been sustained for the term of social responsibility which has diverse definition for it, but ISO had given the rough definition on the current which was provided before in practice for the CSR is described as “The accountability of the organization is dependent on the activities and decisions which should be transparent and morale based that contributes in supportable development.” ” (ISO 26000:2010). The organization does not have economic profit that enterprise does not automatically translated for the social responsibilities but the profit is dependent of the creativities of the consumers calculation that are related to the business accomplishments which are not simply act. It is very necessary for the organizations revenue to create a healthy and safe environment that addresses the verity and encourages for the fair distribution on ethical manner. (Zulfiqar 2019). The most expostulation for the organization is how to handle the balance that works for the parties. The capabilities of the business is totally dependent on the shareholders and investors for the social corporate responsibility and it should be continued for the growth of the organization.

In the recent world with the speedy development of mankind it has been observed the issue of the environmental pollution has been increased with distinct ratio. The foundation of the country’s social and economic stability is the revolution of the green development in industrial sector (Shao, Luan, & Yang, 2016). Furthermore the industrial-technological progress, central economics and ecological protection are focused on the green productivity which are significant progression in the development and the developed countries. (Chen, 2014).

Nevertheless, the approaches for the green environmental projection is dependent on the temporary and long standing are achieved simultaneously. The perception for the supportable development had some financial factors for the corporate environment behavior (CEB) (Andreou & Kellard, 2020). There should be need of greenhouses gases which helps in the reduction of polluted environment. The organization’s performance is totally dependent of the greenhouse. Although the cost for this greenhouse is very expensive which showed the environmental behaviors (Saha & Dahiya, 2020). Determined that there is bigger blockade for the CSR activities that should be handled financially and ethical way which increase the production and adopt the methodological thoughts for the leadership. (Hawn & Chatterji, 2018).

The modernization of environmental stated as the methodology required more hard work that includes the activities for the suppliers and the clients and the research network partners for the organization. On the other side of the coin the healthy environment is dependent on decreasing the pollution emission in

environment. This can be controlled by employing the reduction pollutant plant which decreases the pollution and makes the environment healthy (M & J, 2007).

Corporate social responsibility (CSR):

There is a planned proper definition of corporate social responsibility (CSR) by quarrelling that “the activities of the social and environmental apprehensions depends on the business operation and connections of the stakeholders which are performed on voluntary basis of the cooperate sustainability and CSR” as per the statement of this author he had defined the performances of the CSR apprehension about five dimensions that are: Voluntariness, stakeholders, social, environmental and economics. Furthermore, in this literature he has not been cleared about the relationship between the responsible origination and CSR. In many studies it had been showed that it had negatively impact on the probability by increasing the higher production which are interlinked with environment and key obligations of the activities. (Marrewijk, 2003).

For corporate social responsibility it is very much necessary that they should integrate the stakeholder theory because it boosts the businesses which contributes in the sustainability of the business through the social act responsibility. It is important for the business that they should adopt such programs which helps them in their succession as well as in sustainability. (Torugsa.N.A, 2013)

These cover the environmental implications of a company's operations:

- Eliminate waste and emissions
- Maximize the efficient use of resources and productivity
- Minimize activities that might impair the enjoyment of resources by future generations.

Corporate Social and Environment Responsivities (CSER):

The issues of the global awareness for social and environmental have increased in current years, and it effects the sensitivity of the social and environmental according to firm’s perspectives. Global warming issues are generated because of these cooperate firms and they usually do not focus that it effects the environment also. Their management is not working on the waste management and did not get follow up their waste management which is the major factor the global warming. (Jayanti.R, 2014)

The perception for the environmental and social reasonability have started to become answerable in traditional corporate annual reports though the disclosure. These firms generate every year their reports and these reports are the key component for the successful organization and the performance of corporate social and environmental is through the disclosure which is linked to the greater financial profile. There is high impact of these reports in which they put their all indicators to show their performance. This type of reporting plays a vital role in their high profile. (Faboyede.O, 2011)

It has investigated that by applying the CSER, the adaptation of the reporting in the corporate social and environmental strategy has multiple advantages. Numerous writers have categorized the elements of corporate social and environmental strategy which is active and submissive. It is also necessary that by applying the environmental management system has a positive influence on their performance. (Sambasivan.M, 2013) The green items and other amenities have adopted to their business practices to incorporate the policies and procedures for corporate social and environmental responsibility which leads to the idea for the industries to enhance the sustainable business. For corporate social and environmental firms, it is necessary to work on waste management and environment management which had positive effects on their business. (Egri.C, 2008)

Corporate social and Environmental responsibility goals should focus on reducing your impact on the planet, using only renewable and recyclable resources where possible. Typical goals might include reducing water consumption, improving management of hazardous waste, or cutting your corporate carbon footprint. (Lund.T, 2004)

Nowadays, corporate social and environmental responsibility CSER has become a priority issue of the government agenda. This has changed government’s capacity to act and impact on social and environmental issue in their relationship with the companies, but also affected the framework in which CSER public policies are designed. Governments are incorporating multi stakeholder strategies. These companies gain the political advantages also (Buckley, 2010). If we talk about the social context, we can find the following:

Corporate citizenship refers to a company's responsibilities toward society. The goal is to produce higher standards of living and quality of life for the communities that surround them and still maintain profitability for stakeholders. The demand for socially responsible corporations continues to grow, encouraging investors, consumers, and employees to use their individual power to negatively affect companies that do not share their values. (Dodds.R, 2010)

Responsibility towards Management:

It is the responsibility of the manager to have a close contact with their customers, consumers, and stakeholder and with the government. It is necessary to have closed relationship with them in order to enhance the performance of the firm. In terms of corporate social and environmental relationship there should be strong relationship with the stakeholders and government so they can improve themselves and sustain the business (Ayuso.S, 2006) however, corporate social responsibility since the start of it is very beneficial for the organization on their image building in the society and in the proximity. Globalization and concept of product competition is created new aspects of socially recognition by the defined by the corporate social responsibility areas. Environmental aspect is one the mostly covered aspect of CSR when it comes to the companies that are polluting environment with the toxic release. Bilge Berkhan Kastaci 2018.

In chemical and manufacturing industries most of the human resource is at risk because the unhealthy environment and safety of the workers. They usually do not focus on their health to minimize the cost for their health and other benefits from the welfare (Lin, Wang, & Wu, 2017).

It is reported that if an organization implements the CSER activities it will reduce the cost of the expenditure and will have low risk which results in sustainable business and development (Gupta, Gupta 2020)

The evidence for the investing in the total quality management it has the direct, notable remarkable impact on the social environment investment by (Abbas 2020).

The relationship between the eco-innovation and social responsibility

has directly impact on the awareness for the mental health and environment which overcome the consumption of the time and production by (Severo et al 2018).

It also has been observed that social expectations are variant and reoccur in discrimination which effects the organizational activities. There should be respect for the human rights and sustainability of the environment. First its focused was on environment only then it was reclassifying and added education, charity and social concerns. It was first developed for the larger organization soon it was implemented by small and medium enterprises (Li-Pin, Lina, & Fu-Chen, 2018).

Role of the cost and budget management:

The role of the cost and budget management, it is necessary for encounter the both external and internal cost for the CSER activities because it has the direct/indirect impact on their expenditures. For the sustainability of the industry they need to manage the expenditure cost of the CSER activities and it plays vital role in development and profitability (Bhardwaj, Chattrjee, Demir, & Turut, 2018).

Theories of CSR:

There are several theories on CSER that can explained their finding with the help of these theories. These theories gone through the different process and published in their annual year reports which also includes their financial statements. This is why the companies are interested in their CSER activities and their stakeholders are taking interest in such activities for the performance of their business. The most common theories are given as Below:

1. Political Economy theory
2. Stakeholder theory
3. Ethical theory
4. Impression management theory
5. Legitimacy theory

Political Economy theory:

According to the researcher perspective the activities of the CSER from the economic viewpoint that reporting is happening with in the political framework and context (Gray, Owen, & Adams, 1996). The authors also mentioned that the firm has power to stimulus the equilibrium of the market. Social powers of the firm are internally and externally without destroy power. CSER is mostly affected by the different

influences of the political pressures and social sources (Deegan & & Unerman, 2006) .

Stakeholder theory:

The stakeholder's theory is the most famous and one of the oldest theories that is most important for the both companies and the society which defines the financial statement and the performance of the business. As there are many groups of the stakeholder so this business is affected by many parties over the many years (Crowther, 2004) These different groups like shareholders, creditors, consumers, suppliers and many more have their different interest on their human rights and the work for the community (Alam, 2006). The author also focused on the responsibility of the basic principles that combines together in the organization for the conclusion (Garriga and Mele 2004).

Ethical theory:

This theory is defined by the authors that it shows the relationship between the society and the business on the principles of the ethics which shows things to do on right and fair base which is good and essential for the community (Garriga and Mele 2004). This theory is applied on the stakeholders, investors, suppliers and employees. This is most and vital for the organization to make their standards on the basis of ethics.

Impression management theory:

The author explained this theory as the nature of the CSER in respect to impression management. The impression management is defined as the discipline of psychology. CSER is mostly in qualitative nature so this theory can be done in narrative form. There is no particular framework for this theory as CSER is always in narrative form so this does not need any framework to initiate the CSER activities. According to (Brennan, Guillamon-Saorin, & Pierce, 2009) the impression management is to control on individuals and should control on the people's interest. The main objective of this impression management is to handle the self-representation (Jaworska & Bucior, 2017) . In order to create the positive and clear image for the stakeholders they only disclosed selective information. The purpose of this theory is to avoid the gap of the legitimacy (Ahmad, 2019).

Legitimacy theory:

This is most important and widely used theory in CSER research. The origin of the theory is from the social contract (Deegan 2006). In this theory it defines that how the organization is taking part in the activities of the society and how it is operating in terms of their business. This is very much important for an organization to take part in such activities where the communities are involved. This is also good for their business and it also can eliminate the gap of the legitimacy in the society. The worse cause for the legitimacy gap there should be political influence, banning on the products, lawsuit and incomplete or the rejection of the consumers (Hossain, 2017). In the light of (Freedman & Jaggi, 2005) is to grip on social and political pressure to avoid the legitimacy gap. This may improve the performance and create the good image and fulfill the expectation of the stakeholders and community.

Chapter 3

Conceptual Framework:

According to literature the relationship between CSR activities and its impact on social environment. Conceptual framework is a theory which makes a logical sense among the activities performed by the organization and its impact on environment. Following is the conceptual framework diagram which shows relationship.

Sources of waste material

Waste Management is a very challenging task for any pharmaceutical companies. There are different examples of waste management. This needs special treatments for this waste management

1. Vitamins and supplement
2. Hazardous drugs
3. Non-hazardous drugs
4. Creams and Ointments
5. P-listed

Waste Management Procedures:

The procedure adopted by the pharmaceutical companies have the following steps:

1. Segregate pharmaceutical waste from biohazardous waste
2. Pull out all controlled substance
3. Pull out any trace chemotherapy waste.
4. Pull out any hazardous waste
5. Package what's left

Contract with a licensed biomedical waste disposal services are also included to handle these types of the waste material.

Company Reputation:

The reputation of the organization because in market there are many competitors who want to enhance the business and get the reputation in market by adopting the CSER activities. It observed that it has direct or indirect impact on the reputation of the organization. It is dependent by its external and internal stakeholders who are vitally important and have good relationship with them. Most common factors for the reputation of the organization in a corporate sector. They are:

1. Ethical/Moral obligations
2. Employee work place
3. Brand recognition
4. Social Responsibility
5. Customer Loyalty
6. Voluntary in community

CHAPTER 03 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction:

To the analysis of the data this chapter covers the details about the techniques and methodologies. There are the different methods for the collection of the data by using the questionnaire and other sampling techniques. This chapter may also include the research approach and design the different formats for the data analysis. To collect the primary data for the research it is very much important to start the survey questionnaire which should be designed by focusing the main objectives of the research. The scales and measurements are used for the designing the questionnaire which may adopt the main objectives and identify the different practices by CSER (Corporate Social Environment Responsibility) approaches, environmental pollution, waste management and the relation between CSER initiatives and company reputation and performance.

The need for the questionnaire is to get the desire data and this may include as a piece of the information so

that the research can be explained properly and analyze with clear vision. The data which is being collected will always be confidential and will be used for the voluntary nature of the participation.

There are different variables which are used to measure the overview of company. In this regard the questionnaire is designed by focusing four sections. The section is started with getting the information about the CSER and what is the level of their knowledge about CSER, also its importance. It also covers how CSER is important for the company and how it impacts on environment.

Third section contained questions which help to assess the waste management process which includes both solid and liquid waste material. It also covers where that waste management process started and where it has to be end. Fourth section consists of questions related to company reputation how CSER has direct/indirect impact on society. Few last questions were about the measures should take by the company to initiate CSER in cooperate sector.

Research Approach:

For achieving the objectives of present research study (Muhammad, 2012), gives the relation between the corporate responsibility and its performance. This study is based on mixed methods which shows qualitative, interview based and quantitative approach for applying the different variables. This research method shows that corporate social responsibility which have positive effect on their financial performance and reputation of the organization. In the 1970s and 1980s, qualitative and quantitative research were seen as two opposing paradigms, each with its own set of supporters, the majority of whom would have denied the possibility of mixing the two values. However, from the last two centuries the data is collected by the mixed data. (Jogulu and Pansiri, 2011).

There are the different methods for the identification of the data. Most well know and famous method for the data collection which is widely used is a mixed method. It is widely extended in different fields like health and medical sciences and some other fields also. The method is now commonly used and improved over the last many centuries and develop a wide range of the questions. Basically this method is used to get accurate data and is designed stipulating the shorthand notation system which may include the different procedures like fields, visualization, pictorial and diagrammatic by creating the rational of the performing the different mixed methods and should study all the procedures for the getting the data from the research.(Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011).

Quantitative Research

For three objectives, series fifty questionnaires were distributed among two Pharmaceutical organizations that is Archroma and GSK based at Jamshoro district. However, 39 questionnaires fully filled were received back with response rate (78%). The technique was used for the collection of the data is quantitative statistical.

Qualitative Research

The qualitative research encompasses a set of texts and/or auditory and visual evidence(e.g. records or field notes) (e.g. recordings of interviews, focus groups or consultations). Recordings are transcribed in paper so that they can be analyzed in depth, connected to and/or coded with analytical notes. (Julia.B, 2008)

Research Design

In its most basic form, research design is a set of methods and procedures for collecting and analyzing events (data of the variables specified in the problem research), and it can be thought of as a framework for organizing and responding the research question. There are three types of research designs: explanatory, exploratory, and descriptive.

This is an exploratory research project. As the name implies, this type of research is conducted to investigate or explore the research question. Exploratory research is very useful in laying the initial groundwork that will lead to additional research because it is responsive to change.

QUALITATIVE RESEARCH METHODS

Different interviewing techniques are used in observational qualitative research to get from the survey, such as focus group, organized interviews, semi-structured interviews, open-ended interviews

QUANTITATIVE RESEARCH METHODS

Different interviewing techniques are used in observational qualitative research to get from the survey, such as focus group, organized interviews, semi-structured interviews, closed-ended interviews

RESEARCH TECHNIQUE

The way a researcher understands the point of view of another person is defined as qualitative analysis. This research uses the methodology of content analysis to consider and transcribe the experience of another person. The method used to make extraordinary and true assumptions by reading and coding textual material is by definition content analysis. Documents, oral conversation and graphics can be included in the content. Primary interview data is the key source of this study, thus the recorded, transcribed and analyzed data.

TARGET POPULATION

The target population for this research is the Pharmaceutical multi-national company GSK Glaxo Smith Kelvin which reside in district Jamshoro and also another popular company that is Archroma besides GSK. The organization is layered in three categories that is Upper management, middle management and lower management.

SAMPLING TYPE AND TECHNIQUE

In order to collect proof for the study's goals, I focused on a specific demographic. Many researchers do not have the time or resources to examine the entire population, as is common practice, so they use sampling methods to eliminate or reduce the number of cases in the population. At the end of this research results are considered as generalized for whole the targeted population.

There are two types of sampling methods in general: 1) probability sampling and 2) non-probability sampling. In Probability sampling, any case in the population has an equal right or chance of being included in the sample. Probability sampling, on the other hand, can be divided into four categories: 1) simple random sampling, 2) stratified sampling, 3) multi stage sampling.

In Non-probability sampling every single person in that population do not have an equal right or chance to be added in research sample. This type only implies with the case studies and research design of qualitative research. There are five kinds of this technique: 1) quota sampling 2) Convenience sampling 3) purposive sampling 4) Self-selection sampling and 5) snowballing sampling.

With reference to use of the sampling techniques non-probability sampling is chosen for this, for the data collection of objective 1, and objective 2. From various sampling techniques non-probability is chosen for objective 1, objective 2 and objective 3

DATA COLLECTION TOOLS

The data collection tools and analysis are the most important aspects of any research. Both, if carried out with sincerity, could provide an outcome to the research question. Interviews, focus groups, observational methods, and document analysis are some of the data collection tools used in qualitative research methodology. Data gathered via the interviews or focus groups is videotaped or recorded in audio format. Then transcribed into text for further analysis.

Primary Data

The data collection used for this research to get primary data is the formal semi-structured open-ended interviews. The respondents gave the researcher a chance to get interviews in their office. Collecting the data along interviews is so popular for researchers, because it gave us an advantage one-on-one verbal communication in order to get reliable information that the researcher wanted to.

Secondary Data

The secondary data is the one that we do not collect from the concerned interviewers, but from secondary sources from the internet, e.g. books, government census reports, websites, newspapers, Media articles or

research journals. The secondary data for this research is carried from internet in order to support primary data.

TRANSCRIBING

Qualitative research data is gathered on two-way influence tactics that can involve verbal and non-verbal interaction in this communication. In the form of audio or video recordings, much of the qualitative evidence is obtained. The collected data was then further transcribed for further analyses in text form.

Language

The initial phase towards face to face communication are interviews, there were informal languages Sindhi and English used during conduct of interviews according to the mode of respondents. Sindhi language was mostly used during conduct of interview in which respondents had confidence to answer the research questions more accurately rather than in English after the interview concluded the data was translated into English and transcribed.

Sample Size

The selected sample size was 50, the number of samples that responded back was 39 including males as well as females. And 5 in-depth interviews were being recorded.

Pharmaceutical company of Jamshoro (GSK/ARCHROMA)	
Population	800+
Questionnaire Distributed	50
Received	44
Discard	05
Complete Forms Received	39
Total Sample Size	39

Table "1" show sample size.

3.7 Questionnaire and its design

This research is based on data collected from a self-reported questionnaire which was composed of multiple questions.

The questionnaire was composed of 06 items, 02 environmental pollution, 02 waste management, 02 CSER initiatives and reputation. The questionnaire is attached in the Appendix section at the end of this thesis.

3.9 Data Collection

The data was collected through survey questionnaire from upper, middle, and lower management that were known to the company policies and procedures. Questionnaires were distributed to both organizations for the reason to get correct and relevant information that is required for this research study.

The primary data was collected through official websites, internet, and officials. Questionnaires were given physical and online to 50 sample questionnaires were distributed out of which 39 participants responded back. And 05 in-depth interviews are conducted for the authentication of results.

3.10 Summary

The chapter gives the brief description of specific procedures and techniques carried out to collect, select, process and analyses data for present study. This enables to evaluate the study's overall validity and reliability.

Chapter 4

DATA ANALYSIS

The initial step in the procedure of data analysis is to “know your data”. When the audios are perceived entirely, later on transcribed on the paper and converted into text form then the procedure of reading and critical thinking is started. This is basically procedure of getting familiar with the collected data, it helps the researcher to get an idea about the given data. After this the process of scrutinizing the data in systematic manner starts.

Formal qualitative data processing requires several measures that eventually weed out sections (concepts) that lead to the response to the research question. After knowing the data the process, initial coding takes place; second coding step is sorting. This involves revisiting the initially codes that were made. Therefore, this stage allows to sort out

Certain similar codes that can be integrated and renamed into several other codes. Then time comes for arranging the codes in categories; this help to understand the researcher which code is particularly relating in which category. Forth step is to oversee the initial list; this is literally sifting where the researcher filter out the less important codes the final stage is to transform categories into concepts. (Meaning.D, 2007).

QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS

Overall population:

To identify how the environment is effected by the disposal of waste management by the company, results indicate that there is 90% male and 10% female employee response on the required information. In addition to that the 23% is of 20 to 30 years of age, 60% is of 31 to 40 and above 40 and 17% who were working on both organizations.

The population covered during my research there were 50% are upper management, 30% are middle management and 20% are lower management.

4.2 Objective 01

To explore the sources of environmental pollution in pharma sector of Jamshoro.

In order to analyze the data of first objective I have observed that there are different sources for the pollution which are mild dangerous and most dangerous for the environment. When I asked about the sources 20% were replied that “vitamins and supplements” 24% were replied in “Hazardous Drugs” and 56% replied in “Creams and ointments”.

Furthermore, we asked them if your organization dumped in waste by burring or lying the outside, the environment got polluted so what methods should be used by your organization. 36% answered by saying that ETP (Effluent Treated Plan) is good method, 20% replied that Incineration (Waste to energy) is better method, 16% answered that Pyrolysis is the good method for disposal and in last 28% answered that recycling is best way of disposal which can be done on very low cost.

Objective 2

To evaluate the methods of waste management adopted by the pharma companies.

To check the performance about the waste management employee had been asked some indicative questions about the disposal of the waste management and keeping the environment clean in which 52% shows their interest in yes it is our responsibility to make the environment healthy, 28% were answered that its not necessary but we can use it as choice and similiary 20% were not believed that this is any reponsibility but it can be a option for us to make the environment clean.

To obtain the second objective of my research I Further asked about how the organization is taking the

initiatives to adopt the CSER activities. 56% asked that the organization is working for the community voluntarily, 28% told that they also should improve the labor polices and 20% that the company should take initiative about the fair trade.

Objective 3

To study the relation between CSER initiative and company’s reputation and performance by evaluating two companies of Jamshoro district.

To enhance the improvement and reputation of the organization they have taken some initiatives in which 32% were answered that it depends on “Better Brand Recognition” 20% were told that to improve the image of the company they need to increase the sales and the customers loyalty, 48% told that to enhance the reputation of the company they must have strong relationship and work for the social cause.

I asked the employees about the impact of CSER activities how your company is better than your competitors. 44% of the employee said that there should be moral obligation in order to compete our competitors, 36% were replied that there should be good will and good image of the organization and in last 20% were believed that if the organization increases their creativity, they can compete their competitors.

QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS

The interviews were taken in expressive format in which the interviewee gave different answers as per their information. It was firstly taken as audio and converted into the transcription to get the desire data. As per the authors believe that transcription data can be worked as complete information given by the responders. This information can be very much helpful and understand able for the further process.

Adam (2011) specified that it is very easy for the researcher to understand the answers given by the interviewee and when it comes to transcribing it is quite easy to omit the unnecessary information from that interview in verbal speech patterns. If the respondent is using its mother language other English then he may response more accurately in his native language. After a detailed interview the researcher can evaluate the data which is to be transcribed and convert it its conventional language that is understandable for everyone. When the translation is completed, the researcher may use the different grammatically software's to identify the grammar errors done by the researcher. This all happened because the researchers may cross the less errors on the ground and get the maximum answers or responses as given by the respondents. The intensions of the researchers is very cleared and transparent for analyzing the data with minimum or no error that may harm the data or research. For the analysis of the data the researcher uses the apparent content analysis technique. The data analysis is divided into four parts: coding, sorting, sifting and theme information. The details of these parts are explained in the next sections in detail.

5.3.1 CODING

It is very important to understand the transcription and must have grip on the data to understand the importance of the transcription to convert it in coding form. Whatever the information he gathered from the respondent the researcher will transcribe that data without being unbiased and believing that the data is purely on merit. The data is read by him again and again to avoid the miss data and check the vital data

should be processed. The data is then analyzed and when it comes to fullness the data was underlined or painted by the meaningful units and marked as important data by distinguishing the different colors. The highlighted data can be varied from unit to unit and some time it can be of the same length depending on the given data. It is necessary and depends on the respondent that whatever they want to give the data and how they express the data and how they feel about the question as per their knowledge and discuss openly by sharing the information with the researcher. Furthermore the vital information is converted and assigned the different codes to them for the identification of the data. The data can be a word, a phrase or it can be a thought which is given by the respondent in the native language or visual which is used for the coding. (Saldana, 2009). The process of coding was repetitive for as many times as the ample quantity of information was gathered from every transcript. This process is important for the researchers and was carried on inductively.

5.3.2 SORTING

This stage entailed the reorganization of some of the initial codes as well as the addition of additional codes. Fresh relevant units (codes) were uncovered, just as they were with a new session of re-reading. Some of the meaning units were quite little, while others were rather large. The researcher next filtered the codes that were similar or redundant, keeping the research issue in mind. After that, the codes were renamed.

5.3.3 SIFTING

Following the sorting of the codes, the data is sifted further. This entails selecting the most pertinent codes. This aids in the organization of the essential codes into topics. It is important to note that the transcriptions lacked sub themes, which are the same as the codes of the meaning units in the manifest content analysis (Bengtsson, 2016).

5.3.4 THEMES FORMATION

The themes were developed after the careful sifting of the codes into the categories. These themes helped to understand the problem and contributed to answer the research question. The themes created from the analysis of primary data correlated with those obtained from the secondary data, because of the reality that the secondary data is already used.

5.4 ANALYSIS OF OBJECTIVES

Following are the main three objectives of the research:

1. To explore the sources of environmental pollution in pharma sector of Jamshoro.
2. To evaluate the methods of waste management adopted by the pharma companies.
3. To study the relation between CSER initiative and company's reputation and performance by evaluating two companies of Jamshoro district.

The source of the primary data is extracted by using the techniques of content analysis themes. **5.4.1 PROCESS OF CONTENT ANALYSIS**

The outline or content for the analysis can be illustrated as given below and some of the data can be shown through the appendixes. This data is widely used for the purpose of analyzing the questionnaires designed to get the appropriate and accurate data.

Transcribe and Translation

The interviews were conducted in audio format then it was converted and translated to get the desired data. Furthermore, for the process of demonstration we have used some important information as mentioned below.

1. What are the sources of pollution in pharma sector and which ones are the most dangerous?
2. How do you deal with hazardous waste? What is/are the best methods?
3. In your opinion, waste management and keeping the environment clean is your responsibility or a choice/option for you?
4. If this is responsibility, then what extra initiatives you take to make waste management as CSER practices?
5. How does keeping the environment clean help in improving your reputation in the market?
6. How are your company's CSER initiatives better than your competitors'?

Interviewee 1	Interviewee 2	Interviewee 3	Interviewee 4	Interviewee 5
<p>1. The sources for the waste are: Hazardous drugs</p> <p>2. The best method for disposal is (Incineration) waste to energy</p> <p>3. Yes, It is a primary responsibility</p> <p>4. The initiative should be plantation for the community</p> <p>5. For the reputation of the company there should be customer loyalty</p> <p>6. To defeat the competitors there must be moral obligations</p>	<p>1. The sources for the waste are: Vitamins and Supplements</p> <p>2. The best method for disposal is EPA (Environmental Protection Agency)</p> <p>3. Yes, It is my responsibility.</p> <p>4. The organization should work on labor policies</p> <p>5. The organization must be self-serving and there must be brand recognition</p> <p>6. The organization should work on goodwill and image to overthrow the competitors.</p>	<p>1.The sources for the waste are: Creams and ointments</p> <p>2. The best method for the disposal is Pyrolysis.</p> <p>3. No, It is not my responsibility but should take it as option.</p> <p>4. The initiative should be taken by the organization is to work on policies for the workers.</p> <p>5. For the reputation there is need of good relationship with the customers.</p> <p>6. To defeat the competitors the company should take initiative on creativity.</p>	<p>1. The sources for the waste are: Hazardous drugs</p> <p>2. The best method for the disposal is ETP(Effluent Treated Plant)</p> <p>3. No, I will take it as option but not a responsibility.</p> <p>4. The company should take initiative in participating in fair trade.</p> <p>5. For the reputation of the organization it must work on their sales and brand image.</p> <p>6. The organization should work on social cause like charity and needy people to defeat its competitors.</p>	<p>1.The sources for the waste disposal are: Creams and ointments</p> <p>2. The best method for the waste disposal is recycling.</p> <p>3. Yes, It is my legally responsibility.</p> <p>4. The company should take initiative and took part in volunteering community.</p> <p>5. For the reputation of the organization it should work loyalty and long term relationships with the customers.</p> <p>6. For the better recognition and defeat the competitors the company should seriously work on cleanliness of water and roads and schools rehabilitation.</p>

Coding

The answers were given in descriptive form are the changed into meaning full codes:

Interviewee 1	Interviewee 2	Interviewee 3	Interviewee 4	Interviewee 5
<p>1. The sources for the waste disposal are: Hazardous</p> <p>2. The best method for disposal is Incineration (waste to energy)</p> <p>3. Yes, It is a primary responsibility</p> <p>4. The initiative should be plantation for the community</p> <p>5. For the reputation of the company there should be customer loyalty</p> <p>6. To defeat the competitors there must be moral obligations</p>	<p>1. The sources for the waste disposal are: Vitamins and Supplements</p> <p>2. The best method for disposal is EPA (Environmental Protection Agency)</p> <p>3. Yes, It is my responsibility.</p> <p>4. The organization should work on labor policies</p> <p>5. The organization must be self-serving and there must be brand recognition</p> <p>6. The organization should work on goodwill and image to overthrow the competitors.</p>	<p>1.The sources for the waste disposal are: Creams and ointments</p> <p>2. The best method for the disposal is Pyrolysis.</p> <p>3. No, It is not my responsibility but should take it as option.</p> <p>4. The initiative should be taken by the organization is to work on policies for the workers.</p> <p>5. For the reputation there is need of good relationship with the customers.</p> <p>6. To defeat the competitors the company should take initiative on creativity.</p>	<p>1. The sources for the waste disposal are: Hazardous</p> <p>2. The best method for the disposal is ETP(Effluent Treated Plant)</p> <p>3. No, I will take it as option but not a responsibility.</p> <p>4. The company should take initiative in participating in fair trade.</p> <p>5. For the reputation of the organization it must work on their sales and brand image.</p> <p>6. The organization should work on social cause like charity and needy people to defeat its competitors.</p>	<p>1.The sources for the waste disposal are: Creams and ointments</p> <p>2. The best method for the waste disposal is recycling.</p> <p>3. Yes, It is my legally responsibility.</p> <p>4. The company should take initiative and took part in volunteering community.</p> <p>5. For the reputation of the organization it should work loyalty and long term relationships with the customers.</p> <p>6. For the better recognition and defeat the competitors the company should seriously work on cleanliness of water and roads and schools rehabilitation.</p>

Sources of Environment Pollution Initiatives and Reputation

Waste Management

Company

Sorting

In this step the data was sorted from the descriptive data and is converted this information in coded form which covers the main three objectives of the study. The sorted data is given as below:

Interviewee 1	Interviewee 2	Interviewee 3	Interviewee 4	Interviewee 5
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hazardous • Incineration (waste to energy) • Yes, responsibility • Plantation for the community • Customer loyalty 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vitamins and Supplements • EPA (Environmental Protection Agency) • Yes, responsibility. • labor policies • self-serving 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creams and ointments • Pyrolysis. • No, option. • Policies for the workers. • good relationship • Creativity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hazardous • ETP(Effluent Treated Plant) • No responsibility. • Fair trade. • Sales and brand image. • social cause charity needy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creams and ointments • Recycling. • Yes, responsibility. • Volunteering community. • loyalty long term relationships • Cleanliness of

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moral obligations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> brand recognition goodwill image 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> people 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> water and roads and schools rehabilitation.
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Sifting

From the above data after sorting there were changes made according to the frequency of duplication of responses.

1. Hazardous
2. Creams and Ointments, drugs
3. Labor Policies
4. Work for Community
5. Brand Image
6. Responsibility
7. Relationship with customers

Theming

The themes for the data is derived from the apparent content analysis of the developed data, which is relevant to objective 1:

1. Untreated creams, pills, drugs main source of environmental pollution:

According to the respondents, the major hazardous items which lead to high environmental pollution and threat to humans and the ecosystem include all untreated waste from the pharmaceutical companies especially creams, pills, drugs disposed without treatment.

2. Incineration, recycling, Effluent Treatment Plant mitigate environmental pollution

The most widely utilized waste management and treatment techniques include incineration, recycling, and treatment plants with recycling being the most beneficial for the company in monetary terms and society.

3. Conserving the environment as a moral responsibility

Environmental conservation is considered by many employees as a moral obligation towards the society and the planet. Some respondents even considered it as legal obligation while few termed it as an option and goodwill gesture towards society.

4. Community volunteering as a step towards Corporate social environmental responsibility

Community volunteering activities for instance cleaning and tree plantation drives and use of recyclable and biodegradable material for packaging are considered as a positive step towards corporate social environmental responsibility.

5. Creative CSER initiatives provide competitive edge and improved employer branding.

Innovative CSER initiatives which are different from the competitors help create positive company image for the employees and customers alike and provide competitive edge to the company leading the initiative.

Key Findings:

There are different types of the waste material especially creams, pills, drugs disposed without treatment that is being operated by the organization. The most widely utilized waste management and treatment techniques include incineration, recycling, and treatment plants. Some respondents even considered it as legal obligation while few termed it as an option and goodwill gesture towards society. Furthermore I observed that company is serious about taking initiatives and working on different projects like in community they have installed water filtration plant and

operate small schools. Innovative CSER initiatives which are different from the competitors help create positive company image for the employees and customers alike and provide competitive edge to the company leading the initiative. For this purpose they need to work on the moral obligations like donation, helps the needy and work for the community without getting any benefit. It is also necessary to defeat the competitor the organization should build good will and image in the market. Similarly, there is also need to increase the creativity because this market world is dealing with new technologies to get the reputation and make itself the stronger than its competitors.

4.8 Summary

The analysis of the current study is described in this chapter which helps to show that all of the statements developed for study were accepted. Employees wish to work under the umbrella of CSER activities. But the organization felt some challenges to initiate and implement smoothly. Furthermore, this study measures the waste management for the disposal of solid and liquid wastage. They made some policies to handle the wastage by dump in, buried and some of them sent through the containers. And also find out that they know about the environment pollution and its dangerous effects on society.

CHAPTER 05 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS:

5.1 Discussion

There is need to manage and sustain the environment standards which are creating problems for today's generation as well as it will create greater problems for the next generations. Management of waste should be planned, documented, implemented and sustained so that we can save the environment and ecofriendly. Most of the living bodies are in danger due to this dangerous polluted environment that is water, land and air.

5.2 Conclusions

Most of the people not aware of the health and environmental implications of improper disposal. For that purpose, there should be public awareness and training should be arranged time by time. Such training should be done for the staff of the industries and other sectors which are affecting the environment. However, it is necessary that the training should be different for both management and public.

Most of the wastage is not recorded in pharmaceutical companies. They have both solid and liquid wastage. ARCHROMA was burning their waste chemicals and some of them was burring in dump in. This is causing environment more hazardous and dangerous for the community and society. Similarly, GSK uses the technology of waste management by sending their expiry medicines to recycle and sometimes other companies that are specifically designed for the waste management.

Both the companies are well aware of the CSER activities to sustain their business and reputation in cooperate sector. This is very heavy task and costly this is why their activities are very slow.

5.2 Recommendations

This research provides the following recommendations:

- Open burning should be prohibited because there is emission of harmful chemicals is making the environment polluted.
- It is also recommended that Wastewater treatment plants with modern technologies such as ozonation and membrane filtration should be set at industrial premises for those who cannot

afford and get filtered water for themselves. There should be more plantation near the industries for the eliminating the air pollution. There is a recycling process but it should be upgrade day by day with the modern technologies.

- Industries should be supported to set up waste management teams, draft and implement waste management plans. There should be more trainings on waste management and CSER activities to enhance the capacity of the employees. When the new activates to be done employees must need to train first so that they can implement those changes very smoothly. I also recommend that all the industries of the Pakistan should consult and share the activities with the United States environmental protection agency's (U.S.EPA) program 'WasteWise'. It is the plat form for all the organization to enhance the capacity building and well know of the activities as they are forming and implementing.

5.3 Limitations:

When I was doing my search, I found some limitations which are needed to be addressed. Due to the current situation of the COVID-19 I had to follow the strict procedures like social distancing and other protocols given by the organization. When COVID-19 was on its peak. I chose to fill online forms from the management. Similarly, when it was in mild situation. I went there and filled the forms physically within the boundaries of the given protocols. It was very difficult situation for gathering the accurate data and complete my thesis on time.

5.4 Future Research:

As in my search I have chosen two multinational pharmaceutical companies of district Jamshoro. I was bounded with in these two companies and it was my limited search. I believed that search should be done on broader to cover the multinational as well as national level. It was very challenging research because companies were busy in their daily basis activities and due to COVID-19 they also have to follow the protocols. The organization was facing the different challenges like if they implement CSER they need high cost budget so they avoid the activities of CSER. Similarly, the communities were highly affected because of contaminated water and harmful chemicals. This search was done on Archroma and GSK Company of Jamshoro district.

5.5 Summary:

CSER is a very challenging task for all the multinational companies. Its activities are hard to implement by the organization. The organization should adopt the challenges and should train the staff about the activities of CSER. They should well know about waste management and disposal of the harmful chemicals. The communities are highly affected by the hazardous chemicals, water and soil and sea life. The organization should take this matter seriously and worked for the future to avoid these challenges faced by the communities. During my survey I overserved that the organization are willing to work on CSER to enhance their business production and reputation in market. They have done their paper work and to some extent they have started their work and in future they will do more and fully hand practice of CSER activities. They have installed filter plants of water for the community. They had also worked on planation so that the environment of the community should healthy and fresh. They had done many activities for the community like giving masks during covid-19.

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